

Youth Involvement in Agribusiness for Sustainable Economic Development and National Security: A Conceptual Review

1. Otaokpukpu, Justina Njideka

Department of Business Administration and Management, Federal Polytechnic Oko, Anambra State. justinaottah@gmail.com

2. Nwankwo Leopold Arinze(PhD)

Department of Business Administration and Management, Federal Polytechnic, Oko, Anambra State

3. Okonkwo, Chukwudi Joseph (PhD)

Department of Cooperative Economics and Management, Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, Imo State. Jochy2kng@yahoo.com

Abstract

Providing economic opportunities for youth in agribusiness is essential to securing the future of agriculture in Nigeria. However, barriers limit youth involvement in agribusiness and the broader food system. The study aimed to assess the potentials of youth involvement in Agribusiness in Nigeria particularly looking at the opportunities, issues and challenges that could facilitate growth and open up the sectors of the economy for sustainable economic development and national security. The findings showed that existing agricultural interventions are production-centric and provide low-income earnings and inadequate social protection. The study also noted that the youth have pessimistic perceptions about agriculture's capability of improving their living standards. This could be ascribed to the minimal youth involvement in agricultural activities and the youth's shared understanding of the agricultural sector's contribution to general economic growth and national security. From a policy perspective, the literature revealed that current agricultural development programs do not adequately address structural issues underpinning youth involvement in the economy. Therefore, to enhance the involvement of youths in agriculture, there is a need for policy implementation in the area of integrated agricultural-based interventions that are context-specific and promote meaningful youth participation in shaping future food systems.

Keyword: Youth Involvement, Agribusiness, Sustainable Economic Development, National Security

1.1 Introduction

Nigeria, recognized as Africa's most populous nation, is abundantly endowed with both human and natural resources that are widely distributed across the country. Nevertheless, despite these inherent riches, Nigeria continues to grapple with developmental challenges, striving to achieve significant influence on the global stage. These challenges manifest in the form of persistent poverty, incidents of armed robbery, militancy in the Niger Delta region, and the presence of Boko Haram in the Northern region. These complex issues are intricately linked to the limited empowerment of the majority of

Nigeria's youth, (Nnachi, 2012). The prevailing belief among these young individuals is that their nation has not adequately supported them, leading to a sense of disillusionment and a perceived need to respond by not fully contributing to national development. Compounding the issue is the situation where our tertiary institutions annually produce a surplus of graduates without corresponding job opportunities to accommodate them.

Agriculture holds a recognized status as the primary source of livelihood for many rural inhabitants in Africa and is a vital contributor to the region's economic growth. Research conducted by Castañeda, Doan, Newhouse, Nguyen, Uematsu, and Azevedo (2018) underscores agriculture's pivotal role in generating employment, ensuring food and nutrition security, and reducing societal inequalities and poverty in Africa. Furthermore, the agricultural sector offers promising prospects for entrepreneurial endeavors, particularly for youth seeking employment opportunities.

Furthermore, Africa's expanding urban markets offer a fertile ground for heightened demand in processed and prepared food products. This market expansion has the potential to attract substantial private sector investments, benefiting small, medium, and large agribusiness entrepreneurs, as well as other participants in the food system. The realization of the full potential of African agribusiness could unlock markets estimated to exceed US\$100 billion annually by 2025 (Global Youth for Empowerment, 2014).

In contrast to the urban sector, venturing into entrepreneurship within the agriculture sector presents numerous hurdles. These challenges are particularly pronounced for young individuals and encompass issues such as deficient or limited infrastructure, as noted by the Technical Centre for Agricultural and Rural Cooperation in (2016). Additionally, youth grapple with a dearth of access to essential resources, including finance, production inputs, markets, extension services, and training, (Hamidu 2015).

Furthermore, young people often find themselves in competition with older and more established farmers for these limited resources. Within the socio-economic context, farming is often depicted as a profession associated with modest economic returns and lower social status, perpetuating the perception that it is a "poor man's" occupation, characterized by prolonged work hours.

To comprehensively understand the relationship between youth and agricultural development, it is crucial to define the term 'youth involvement.' According to Checkoway (2011), youth participation entails the active engagement and influence of young individuals. It extends beyond mere passive presence or token roles within adult agencies and emphasizes the quality of their involvement, where they have a substantive impact on processes, influence specific decisions, or contribute to favorable outcomes. Importantly, this concept assumes that young people are capable, engaged citizens rather than

passive recipients of services. It further involves young individuals in the institutions and decisions that shape their lives. Consequently, youth participation in agriculture encompasses their engagement in the sector through entrepreneurial activities, participation in value-chain processes, active involvement in policy formulation, and advocacy within structures and systems connected to the food system.

While the active participation of youth is imperative for a nation's economic growth, young individuals encounter additional socio-economic barriers that hinder their engagement in the agricultural sector. These challenges encompass parental discouragement, as parents often steer their children away from farming careers in favor of white-collar professions perceived to offer greater economic rewards and reduced risks. Moreover, many rural youths are compelled to choose farming due to immediate needs, limited employment prospects, or the assurance of inheriting land. In such cases, their involvement is circumstantial rather than aspirational, and they frequently migrate to urban areas in pursuit of a "better life" when opportunities arise (Chinsinga & Chasukwa, 2012).

A growing body of knowledge underscores the importance of implementing multifaceted approaches to promote youth participation in agriculture. This should encompass supportive policies and frameworks that prioritize capacity building, stakeholder investment, and the creation of innovative spaces within agriculture, all while taking into account the aspirations of young people. Such policies and frameworks should be inclusive and acknowledge the pivotal role of young individuals in shaping policy from the outset.

Complementing these policy measures is the Agriculture Promotion Policy (APP) introduced in 2016, marking a significant development in Nigeria's agricultural landscape. Launched on June 21, 2016, by President Muhammadu Buhari, the APP outlines four priority areas (food security, import substitution, job creation, and economic diversification), eleven key objectives, and three thematic interventions designed to unlock the country's agricultural potential. Notably, this policy represents the first instance in Nigeria's history where the issue of agribusiness is explicitly integrated into the agricultural policy. Under the theme of "Crowding in private investment," section 4.2.2 of the APP titled "Agribusiness Development" articulates the prevailing constraints and the government's policy direction regarding agribusiness in Nigeria. Consequently, it is imperative to evaluate whether youth involvement in agribusiness contributes to sustainable economic development and national security in Nigeria.

1.2 Objective of the Study

The objective of this paper is to assess the potentials of youth involvement in Agribusiness in Nigeria particularly looking at the opportunities, issues and challenges that could facilitate growth and open up the sectors of the economy for sustainable economic development and national security.

Conceptual Reviews

Concept of Agribusiness

The term agribusiness simply refers to the breadth of businesses engaged in all aspects of agriculture, from the provision of inputs such as seeds and fertilizer, to farming, processing, marketing, distribution and retail sales. It emphasizes the notion that for agriculture to be sustainable, it needs to be viewed as a business (Yusuff, 2017).

Away from the common traditional system of practice, Agriculture has evolved into Agribusiness and has become a vast and complex system that reaches far beyond the farm to induce all those who are involved in bringing food and fiber to consumers. Agribusiness is defined as the various businesses that are connected with producing, preparing and selling farm products. The term agribusiness was first introduced by Davis and Goldberg in 1957. It represents three part system made up of, *the Agricultural input sector, the Production sector and the Processing manufacturing sector*. Agribusiness includes all stakeholders involved in the value chain which includes the farmer, the agriculture extension workers, institutions and firms that provide the inputs and manufacture food products, logistics services to the market and end consumer. This captures the full meaning of the term “Agribusiness”. It is important to visualize these sectors as interrelated parts of a system in which the success of each part depends heavily on the functioning of the other two.

Today, Agribusiness system has undergone a rapid transformation as new industries have evolved and traditional farming operations have grown larger and more specialized. The transformation did not happen overnight but came slowly as a response to a variety of forces. Knowing something about how agribusiness came about makes it easier to understand how this system operates today and how it is likely to change in the future.

Perspective on Agribusiness in Nigeria

Agribusiness in Nigeria can be defined into two major categories according to Yusuff (2017): Government-Driven and Privately-operated.

A. Government-Driven

Business Incubation Platform (BIP): This facility is housed in the International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA) Ibadan, Oyo State in the Western part of Nigeria. The mode of operation of BIP is

similar to how the chicken egg is incubated. It conceives ideas and needed technologies to drive or transform the sector (Egg), it then provides a favourable condition for their development (Incubation), and then hatch these ideas for the world to use and derive benefit from. The BIP strategy is to support IITA's strategic goals and accelerate the commercial development of IITA's proven and profitable Research for Development (R4D) technologies. It operates on a two-prong commercial development avenue focus where IITA's scientists create Innovative products with the potential for commercialization, and then Initiate & build a network of public and private sector partners that will support the activities of small to medium-scale agribusiness entrepreneurs, initially within Nigeria and later on, elsewhere.

So far, BIP has been able to incubate some Agribusiness Startups in its facility. Some of them are:

GoSeed: This start-up's business operation strategy is charged with the production and marketing of quality breeder and foundation seeds/planting materials.

Nodumax: Provides solution for an improved legumes production. The Nedumax legume inoculant is a product that contains Nitrogen-fixing rhizobia to colonise roots of soybeans and transform the crop into what is termed "Biological Factory".

Aflasafe™: Produce biological control solution that drastically reduces aflatoxin contamination in maize and groundnut. In 2014, the start-up received a seed grant approval from African Union Commission (AUC) and the UNDP to establish the incubation centre in Nigeria. It also made significant progress in Nigeria on the registration, manufacture and commercialization of Aflasafe™, an effective technology for Aflatoxin mitigation in Africa.

B. Private Driven

Unlike what is obtainable in the Information and Telecommunication Sector where the number of Tech Start-ups is much, enjoying support and recognition from Government, there are few privately-operated Agribusiness incubation with start-ups providing a various solution for the sector. Some of the players in this sector include;

Agribusiness Incubation Centre (AIC): The Centre was founded by Premier Agricultural Development Limited (PAD) in 2012 as a hybrid organisation. It is currently in its growth stage.

Basically, PAD conducts its business activities at AIC producing and processing agro-products and providing services all for a fee. It has been able to record remarkable recognition for its unparalleled service. Awards received include; The Federal Government of Nigeria's Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YouWIN) Grant Award in 2012; Batadon community Honours recognition for

contribution to community development award; Building Entrepreneurs Today-3 (BET-3) award by Diamond Bank PLC and EDC/Pan Atlantic University.

AgroHub Agribusiness Incubation Centre: An initiative of Agroinfo Tech Africa, an information and communication Technology Company founded with a primary purpose of adding value to agriculture and agribusiness in Africa using new technologies. The centre is driven by a Public-Private partnership arrangement. Its focuses on Research, Technology and Entrepreneurship where it operates through incubating in-house ideas and embrace disruptive innovations in agriculture that can transform Agribusiness in Africa

Who is a Youth?

There are different descriptions and definitions of who the youth is by different states, organizations and scholars that it is difficult to categorically assert the meaning of the concept youth. However, there is a consensus among scholars that the youths are the leaders of tomorrow and this belief propels countries across the world to pay serious attention to youth development programmes (Mbachu & Alake, 2016).

As cited in the study of Samuel and Deinibiteim (2018), the National Population Commission further describes the defining characteristics of the youth as follows: these are persons who normally would have completed secondary education, and would either be in tertiary institutions such as the university, striving to secure employment, or be already employed. This group of persons would need post-secondary education, employment and reproductive health information and services.

Youth Involvement/Empowerment

It is pertinent to define who a youth is though there seems no universal definition of who a youth is as the term is used differently by individuals, governments and non-governmental organizations. However, the United Nations and Common Wealth of Nations have come up with specific age categories to define a youth. The United Nations uses age category 15-24 years to define a youth while the common wealth uses the age category of 15-29. Most countries have either adopted the UN or common wealth definition. However, in Nigeria, the range is 15-36 years has been taken to be the youth category.

Youth empowerment is an initiative with a view to re-engineering their potentials and energies for peace and stability to reduce poverty, un-employment and criminality. To buttress this view, Chikamnayo (2013) asserted that, self-employment is being driven to the zenith by training and equipping youths with both financial support and the asset base to enhance the growth of their businesses. He further added that the interventionist programme in Abia State has attained enviable height in peace and security

management. In the same vein, National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy, (2005) emphasized in its thrust towards empowering people to improve lives through plans for creating jobs, strengthening the skill base, protecting the vulnerable and promoting peace and security.

Sustainable Economic Development

The term sustainable Development (SD) or sustainable economic development (SED) is a novel concept in the development literature. At one extreme, sustainable economic development is defined as an economic development which meets the needs of present generation and which would not endanger nor compromise the needs of future generation (Nagesha & Subrahmanya, 2016). One of the foremost international bodies advocating economic and environmental sustainability across the globe is the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED). The body defines sustainable development “as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”

Summing up the various definitions given above, the term sustainable economic development can be operationally defined as a strategic process of ensuring that the utilisation of physical environment and its diverse natural resources by nation should be done in a manner that the environment and its resources would provide continuous stream of benefits to both current and future generation. The way Nigeria manages its financial resources as well as its economic resources is economically unsustainable.

The failure of economic growth in most developing and developed countries of Latin America and Africa, in the late 1970s, to deliver corresponding social goods and solve problems of unemployment, poverty, disease, hunger, illiteracy and ever increasing crimes and wars, necessitated the new thinking, and redefinition of development from economic growth centered perspective to human centered approach (Nwanegbo & Odigbo, 2013). In this light, Chandler (2007) sees development as a broader concept that recognizes psychological and material factors that measure human well-being. Development therefore is a multifaceted phenomenon and man centered. It is the process of empowering people to maximize their potentials, and develop the knowledge capacity to exploit nature to meet daily human needs. The transformation of the society and the emergence of new social and economic organizations are critical indicators of development (Nwanegbo & Odigbo, 2013).

National Security

Security of lives and property is the primary responsibility of any responsible and responsive government. As such, most governments take issues of security with all the seriousness it deserves. Security means the state of being free from danger or threat. It is the degree of resistance to or protection

from harm. It applies to any vulnerable or valuable asset, such as a person, dwelling, community (Samuel & Deinibiteim, 2018).

As Holmes (2015) noted, modern concepts of national security arose in the 17th century during the thirty years war in Europe and the civil war in England. In 1648, the peace of Westphalia established the idea that the nation-state had sovereign control not only of domestic affairs such as religion but also of external security. Thom-Otuya (2016) stressed that National security can also be seen as a condition in which citizens of a country enjoy the basic necessities of life. This, obviously, would guarantee some levels of political stability and to a large extent ensure national security in a polity. The study suggested that national security is more than territorial defence and should focus on the “physical, social and psychological equality of life of a society and its members both in the domestic setting and within the large regional and global system”. According to Mathew (1989), as cited in Ojenike, Shodiya and Jolaosho (2016), global development now suggests the need for another analogous broadening definition of national security to include resources, environmental and demographic issues.

The term “security” may be looked at as a state of being protected from danger or anxiety. For a nation, security connotes conditions of peace, stability, order and progress. National security has been construed in different ways, each of which emphasized vital factors underlying ideals. Ochoche (2018) holds that national security focuses on the amassment of military armament, personnel and expenditure. All the above definitions connote that national security has changed overtime. It was expanded to include international economics, long term goals of national development and reconciliation. They are very important for the security of any nation. With this approach, Asad (2019) says “that national security cannot be narrowed down to exclusively military term. Socio economic and cultural aspects, problems of development and modernization, and national integration should be deemed important in considering”.

The Relationship between National Development and National Security

National development and national security are two sides of the same coin. According to Egwu (2016), over the year, the security of the Nigerian nation state was reduced to that of the ruler and his immediate supporters. The country’s leaders rules due to their ill-conceived notions of security. The security calculus of Nigeria State failed because it did not include vital aspect of social and national development, such as the provision of basic social amenities.

Thus, the Nigerian State could not meet the social, economic, or even the military conditions for national security. These problems are clear indication that the government failed to consistently and committed maintains the core social values and physical infrastructure necessary for establishing and sustaining

national security, national survival and socio-political wellbeing of the nation. Nwakpa (2017) asserts the above fact when he says that the increasing national decay and insecurity is seen in the regressing economy, unable health services and facilities, lack of good water, transportation and fuel problems, unemployment and other problems that have overwhelmed the Nigeria society.

From the above, we can see that security is anchored on national development. On the other hand, development can be anchored on security. For instance, the case of violence like ethnic crises, vandalism of pipes and electrical poles, armed robberies, kidnapping and others that cannot be mentioned, have hindered development of some infrastructures and foreign investment. Therefore, we can say that they two cannot be detached.

Issues and Challenges of Youth Involvement in Agribusiness for Sustainable Economic Development and Nation Security in Nigeria

According to Yusuff (2017), available statistics from the FMARD as an outcome of two surveys conducted in 2013, identified the major issues that exist within Nigeria's agribusiness environment while also presenting them according to their perceived ranking level as; Lack of government coordination (100%), inconsistencies in policy, regulatory, laws, taxes and administrative practices (94%), lack of security of raw material supplies to food processors (75%), lack of human capital (50%).

Further analysis by FMARD (2016) revealed the major constraints to be: Absence of appropriate and adaptive processing technology at small scale level; Absence of rural infrastructure to support rural primary processing; Inadequate capacity for processing or crude processing methods; Lack of quality control and standard; Low private sector investment in agriculture/agro-processing; Absence of low cost, market-oriented research prototyping; Inaccessibility and high cost of fund for agro-processing; Low level of capacity of local fabricators; Poor quality of information and irregular dissemination impedes investors' abilities to properly plan investments; No single point of contact: Investors do not know how to find available services and are compelled to interact with resources across multiple MDAs to achieve their objectives; Delivery of Government service are frequently delayed, while contracts and MoUs with MDAs and State Governments can go unfulfilled. These issues calls for government intervention in the sector by addressing focal issues pertaining to policy framework for sector, more political commitment, adoption and utilization of latest agricultural technology, tackle infrastructural deficit, improve financial support and reduce associated risks, reformation and realignment of institutions connected to the agriculture sector so as to be more agribusiness-oriented.

According to Geza, Ngidi, Ojo, Adetoro, Slotow and Mabhaudhi, (2021), the challenges of youth involvement in agribusiness are mostly related to access factors (production resources, finance,

knowledge and information, extension, innovation, and technology) and control over resources. Lack of education, career guidance, employable skills to enter the job market, mentorship, resources, and supportive policies were mentioned as other challenges affecting youth participation in the economy. Using the sustainable livelihood approach, physical capital challenges such as service delivery, access to markets, infrastructure, and low technological advancements were the most dominant. Human and financial capital, that is, access to information and finance and credit, respectively, were mentioned as a challenge affecting youths' involvement. It was interesting to note that social capital was mentioned as a challenge. Youth in agriculture have embraced information and communication technology (ICT) and use different networking platforms such as Facebook, Google, and WhatsApp. Unfortunately, the cost of data has prohibited the full use of ICT for networking.

Empirical Review

Haruna et. al. (2019) studied the challenges and enhancement of youth participation in agricultural education for sustainable food security. The study submits that the phenomenal low participation of youth in agricultural education programmes has featured in several forums both at national and international levels. This is because giving the right opportunity youth could make positive impact and create positive change in the economy of nations. This paper identified challenges and enhancement of youth participation in agricultural education for food security. Survey research design was adopted. The subjects for the study were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using questionnaire. The population for the study comprised of all students in tertiary institutions offering agricultural education programme in the study area. Two hundred and forty tertiary students were chosen through proportionate simple random sampling technique from six randomly selected tertiary institutions in the North Central Nigeria. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data. Findings revealed youths studying agricultural education are aware of their roles through their participation in schools; which extends to their communities, thereby influencing sustainable food supply and availability. The study also revealed that the identified challenges prevail on the youth participating in agricultural education. Analysis of identified approaches had mean scores above the benchmark hence; they were regarded as useful in enhancing youth participation in agricultural education. It was concluded that youth studying agriculture were well aware of their role. Their participation is however, hampered by the enormous challenges bedeviling the programme, which has negative implication on interest by intended youths. The findings were further verified through a focus group discussion involving ten lecturers of agricultural education. It was concluded that youth's participation in agricultural education is hampered by several challenges. The study recommended among others that, Agriculture teachers in collaboration with school management should emphasize

establishment and maintenance of school farms by the students for practical skills acquisition by the youths in school; government should enhance funding, provide scholarship for students to sustain interest and enhance greater youth choice and participation in the programme.

Okonkwo, Chukwudi J. & Ugwa, Magnus (2021), studied empowering youth co-operators for growth in Nigeria, while reviewing working case studies. The study observed that Co-operative as a business encourages youth empowerment around the world, nonetheless in Nigeria its impact is not tangibly felt. This research analysis seeks to identify operating cases of co-operative youth empowerment programmes across the continents and systematically review their strategic objectives and suggest possible aspect to be adopted or tailored to the Nigerian situation. Working cases of co-operative youth empowerment programmes were picked from Asia, Africa, America and Europe. Reviews were systematically done on these aspects; programmes supporting youth co-operative entrepreneurship & youth employment, technology supporting youth innovative sectors, education, awareness raising and networking, policies encouraging co-operative entrepreneurship among young people; international, national or regional policies initiatives. Findings reveal that; working cases starts with observed issues, policy/legal framework and implementation. This is to ensure smooth implementation. Most programmes targeting youth empowerment and entrepreneurship were executed through the Workers co-operative business model so as to fight unemployment and self-reliance. There is unique level of organizational harmony in co-operative activities either between or within a secondary co-operative or tertiary (Apex) co-operative society. Also, programmes were statistically determined as necessary and statistically monitored and evaluated to ascertain levels of achieving set objectives. The study recommends a comprehensive review of existing co-operative laws and regulations across the country with a view to enshrine therein the needs the co-operative youth, incorporate a co-operative youth wing in secondary and tertiary co-operative society across the country and encourage youth participation in the Institute of Co-operative Professional of Nigeria.

Lateef et. al. (2021), investigated Impact of Youth-in-Agribusiness Program on Employment Creation in Nigeria. The study submits that increasing rate of youth unemployment in Africa, particularly in Nigeria, remains among the challenges to social and economic stability. Accordingly, the Nigerian government implemented several interventions, including the Youth-in-Agribusiness (YIA) program to reduce youth unemployment. However, the effect of these programs on gainful employment creation is yet to be documented. Therefore, this study examined the impact of the YIA program on creating gainful employment among the youth. Multistage random sampling was used to obtain cross-sectional data from 668 youth in Southwestern Nigeria. Propensity score matching and endogenous switching probit techniques were used for the estimations. Results indicated that variables such as educational attainment,

access to training, non-agricultural activity, membership in a youth organization, access to credit, productive resources, and youth location were significant and positively influenced youth decision to participate in the YIA program. Furthermore, participation in the YIA program has a significant positive impact on gainful employment among the youth. Therefore, the study recommends that strengthening social capital such as youth organization, credit scheme (financed by private and government), vocational training, and educational system is vital in enhancing participation in the YIA program and eventually gainful employment of youth

In a research study on agricultural transformation, youth participation and food security in Nigeria, Osabohien, et. a. (2020) submits that the study investigated how the agricultural transformation will stimulate youth participation, thereby leading to food security in Nigeria. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) adoption, insurance and health care provision was used as transformation variables. The study applied the Propensity Score Matching (PSM) model on the data sourced from Wave 4 (2018/2019) of the Living Standard Measurement Study-Integrated survey on agriculture (LSMS-ISA). The result showed that; agricultural transformation using ICT, insurance, and health care provision is positive and statistically significant in explaining the level of food security in Nigeria. Therefore, the study concludes that the transformation of Nigerian agriculture should focus on the provision of household's safety net programmes such as insurance. Also, there is a need for the enhancement of households' access to mechanisation services, access to quality and affordability of agricultural input materials to increase productivity, thereby leading to food security.

Opportunities for Youth Involvement in Agribusiness for Sustainable Economic Development and Nation Security in Nigeria

The African Development Bank report of December 2012, in its Country Strategy paper assessing the Agricultural ecosystem of Nigeria and potential for growth between 2012-2016, identified some opportunities within the sector to include; Potential to become a major player in the global economy; Abundant natural resource endowments for agro-allied input production e.g fertilizer; Agricultural and manufacturing potential; Rapid urbanization which represents an opportunity for diversifying income and economic growth; Regional integration. Nigeria is a regional power in West Africa whose economy represents about 55% of West Africa's GDP, and its population of about 167 million provides the largest market in Africa and also abundant human resources and professionals.

Conclusion

Globally, there is a general belief that youth involvement is a necessary tool for achieving real national security and sustainable economic development. This is particularly true for Nigeria where most of the threats to national security are internally generated and propelled. To empower the youths means primarily that an enabling environment must be created for their development and self-actualization as articulated and canvassed by some scholars. The approaches of the government to youth involvement & empowerment and national security are mutually exclusive rather than being mutually inclusive. In the real sense of it, youth involvement and national security policy and programmes should be mutually reinforcing to achieve the desired national security outcomes and sustainable economic development.

References

- Asad, D. (2019). *National affair*. <http://www.nigeriavillagesquare.com>
- Castañeda, A., Doan, D., Newhouse, D., Nguyen, M., Uematsu, H., & Azevedo, J. (2018). World Bank Data for Goals Group. A new profile of the global poor. *World Dev*, 101, 250–267.
- Chandler, D. (2007). The security-development nexus and the rise of anti-foreign policy. *Journal of International Relations and Development*, 10, 362–386.
- Checkoway, B. What is youth participation? *Child. youth serv. Rev.* 33, 340–345.
- Chikamayo, E. (2013). The role of NEVT programme for improving skill acquisition for youth empowerment in Nigeria. *Okene Vocational Education Journal 1* (1) 94
- Chinsinga, B.; Chasukwa, M. (2012). Agricultural policy, employment opportunities and social mobility in rural Malawi. *Agrar. South J. Political Econ*, 7, 28–50.
- Geza, W., Ngidi, M., Ojo, T., Adetoro, A., Slotow, R., Mabhaudhi, T. (2021). Youth participation in agriculture: A scoping review. *Sustainability* 13, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169120>
- Global Partnership for Youth Employment. (2014). Promoting agricultural entrepreneurship among rural youth. Nigeria. <https://iyfglobal.org/sites/default/files/library/GPYE>
- Hamidu, K. (2015). Entrepreneurship intention and involvement in agribusiness enterprise among youths in Gombe metropolis, Gombe state, Nigeria: potentials of agribusiness in Nigeria. *J. Biol. Agric. Health*, 5, 75–84.
- Haruna O. I., Asogwa V. C. & Ezhim I. A. (2019). Challenges and enhancement of youth participation in agricultural education for sustainable food security. *African Educational Research Journal* Vol. 7(4), pp. 174-182, October 2019 DOI: 10.30918/AERJ.74.19.028 ISSN: 2354-2160
- Lateef Olalekan Bello, Lloyd James Segun Baiyegunhi, Djana Mignouna, Razack Adeoti, Paul Martin Dontsop-Nguezet, Tahirou Abdoulaye, Victor Manyong, Zoumana Bamba and Bola Amoke Awotide (2021). Impact of Youth-in-Agribusiness Program on Employment Creation in Nigeria. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/14/7801> Sustainability 2021, 13(14), 7801; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147801>
- Holmes, K. M. (2015). *What is National Security?* 2015 Index of US Military Strength.
- Mbachu, D., & Alake, T. (2016). *Nigeria Population at 182 Million, with Widening Youth Bulge*, AM PST.

- Nagesha, N., & Subrahmanya, B. (2016). Energy efficiency for sustainable development of small industry clusters: What factors influence it? *International Journal of Economic Policy Studies*, 1(1), 133-153
- National Economic Empowerment and Development Startagy (2005). *Youth empowerment. NEEDS@Nigerianeconomy.com*
- Nnachi, A. N. (2012). Youth Employment: Abane to the actualization of the Nigerian government 7-point agenda. *Journal of Arts and Social Nigeria Government*, 1(2), 263-267.
- Nwakpa, E. (2000). *National bar association, deplorers national decay, insecurity*. The Guardian Friday 1 October.
- Nwanegbo, C., & Odigbo, J. (2013). Security and national development in Nigeria: The threat of book haram. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(4), 285-291
- Ochoche, S. (1998). *The military and national security in Africa*. In Hutchful (Ed.) *Military and militarism in Africa*. Senegal: Codesirea
- Ojenike, J., Shodiya, O., & Jolaosho, S. (2016). Youth empowerment and security; A panacea for national development. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 18(4), 120-136
- Okonkwo, C. J., & Ugwa, M. (2021). Empowering Youth Co-operators for Growth in Nigeria: Review of Working Case Studies. *Forshen Hub International Journal of Entrepreneurial and Cooperative Studies*, 3(1), 59–71. Retrieved from <https://journal.forshenhub.com/index.php/FHIJECS/article/view/27>
- Osabohien, Romanus, Oluwatoyin Matthew, Isaiah Olurinola and Busayo Aderounmu (2020). Agricultural transformation, youth participation and food security in Nigeria. *AIMS Agriculture and Food*, 5(4):911–919. DOI: 10.3934/agrfood.2020.4.911 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345943341_Agricultural_transformation_youth_participation_and_food_security_in_Nigeria
- Samuel, K., & Deinbitem, M. (2018). Youth empowerment and national security in Nigeria: issues and prospects. *European Centre for Research Training and Development UK*, 6(3), 1-14
- Technical Centre for Agricultural and Rural Cooperation. (2016). *Youth e-agriculture entrepreneurship*. Wageningen, The Netherlands
- Thom-Otuya, B. (2016). *National security in Nigeria*. Owerri: Institute for Strategic & Development Studies & Priscilla Omama Publishers.
- Yusuff, A. (2017). Agribusiness innovation in Nigeria: Issues , opportunities and options for growth. *International Journal of Research in Business Studies*, 2(1), 269-290